

Short communication

Two new records of Chalcidoidea (Hymenoptera) from Iran

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چکیده

دو گونه از زنبورهای پارازیتوید بالاخانواده Chalcidoidea (Hymenoptera) و همچنین، روابط میزبان-پارازیتویدی آنها روی گیاه *Scariola orientalis* Boissier برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شوند: گونه *Pteromalus sequester* Walker (Hym.: Pteromalidae) پارازیتوید داخلی، انفرادی و لاروی-شفیرگی مگس *Hypenidium oculatum* (Becker) (Dip.: Tephritidae) و گونه *Cerococcus longipilosus* (Archangelskaya) پارازیتوید شپشک *Discodes rubtzovi* Sugonjaev (Hym.: Encyrtidae) (Hem.: Cerococcidae).

Scariola orientalis (Boissier) (Asteraceae) is a perennial, dominant plant species in the steppe and substeppe zones of Iran and usually grown in degrading pastures (Tajali, 2012). Yet, six associations have been made between *S. orientalis* and insects in Iran (Zerova & Seryogina, 2008; Zerova *et al.*, 2008; Moghaddam & Tavakoli, 2010; Melika & Karimpour, 2012; Moghaddam, 2013). This study was conducted to survey the insects associated with reproductive organs of *S. orientalis* in pastures of Yazd province, central Iran, during 2012. The collected specimens of Chalcidoidea (Hym.), Diptera and Hemiptera were identified by the second, third and fourth authors respectively. The specimens are deposited in the insect museums of East-Azarbaijan Research Center for Agriculture and Natural Resources, Tabriz; Qazvin Research Center for Agriculture and Natural Resources, Qazvin; Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection, Tehran and College of Agriculture and Natural Resources of Darab, Shiraz University.

Four species were reared and identified, of which two species of Chalcidoidea and their host-parasitoid-plant associations are newly reported from Iran. The species are as follows:

- *Pteromalus sequester* Walker (Hym.: Pteromalidae)

Material examined – Iran, Yazd province, Darezereshk, N 31°32', E 53°49', 2365 m., 12.iv.2012, 3 ♀♀, 1 ♂;

13.iv.2012, 1 ♀, 2 ♂♂; 14.iv.2012, 1 ♀, 1 ♂; 28.iv.2012, 1 ♀; 9.vi.2012, 1 ♀.

Hosts – Primary hosts. Coleoptera: Apionidae, Chrysomelidae, Bruchinae, Curculionidae; Diptera: Cecidomyiidae; Hymenoptera: Eurytomidae; Lepidoptera: Pyralidae. Parasitoid hosts. *Oedaule italica* Masi (Hym.: Pergidae) (Noyes, 2014); *Hypenidium oculatum* (Becker) (Dip.: Tephritidae) (new host record).

Plant associations – Asteraceae, Caryophyllaceae, Chenopodiaceae, Convolvulaceae, Cupressaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Fabaceae, Malvaceae, Plantaginaceae, Scrophulariaceae, Tamaricaceae, Zygophyllaceae (Noyes, 2014), *S. orientalis* (Asteraceae) (new plant association).

Distribution – Palaearctic, Nearctic, Oriental, Afrotropical, Australasia and Neotropical regions (Noyes, 2014). This species is newly recorded from Iran.

Remarks – The newly recorded species, *P. sequester*, was known as a solitary and larval-pupal endoparasitoid on its primary host, *H. oculatum*. It was responsible for parasitism of about 19.6% of the larvae of *H. oculatum*.

- *Discodes rubtzovi* Sugonjaev (Hym.: Encyrtidae)

Material examined – Iran, Yazd province, Sanij, N 31°38', E 53°92', 2295 m., 17.v.2012, 1 ♀, 1 ♂.

Hosts – Hemiptera: Coccidae (Noyes, 2014), *Cerococcus longipilosus* (Archangelskaya) (Hem.: Cerococcidae) (new host record).

Plant associations – Fabaceae, Rosaceae (Noyes, 2014), *S. orientalis* (Asteraceae) (new plant association).

Distribution – Palaearctic region (Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Czechoslovakia, Hungary, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Russia, Slovakia, former Yugoslavia (pre 1991) (Noyes, 2014) and Iran (new record)).

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Received: 9 June 2014

Accepted: 19 August 2014